

Applying Variations of the Quantitative Feedback Technique (QFT) to Unstable, Non-Minimum Phase Aircraft Dynamics Models

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Abstract

Variations of the Quantitative Feedback Technique (QFT) are applied to a multi-input multi-output (MIMO) flight control problem with unstable, non-minimum phase plants. The linearized state space models represent a forward swept wing aircraft that is inherently unstable. The aircraft dynamic models used here are based on three pitch control surfaces: canards, symmetric flaperons, and strakes. The aircraft modeled here also has a differential canard capability to assist the differential flaperons and rudder in roll and yaw control.

The focus of this paper is to present specialized techniques that enable the designer to achieve acceptable results for effective plants which are both unstable and non-minimum phase. The weighting matrix function is discussed and a method of developing frequency dependent compensation is presented. The unstable open-loop plants require the use of specialized techniques to achieve desired results.

The longitudinal control system, defined as a single-input single-output (SISO) system, is designed using the loop transmission function. The limitations imposed by right-half-plane (RHP) poles and zeros are discussed as the design is presented. A straightforward approach to designing a prefilter is also presented.

Singular-G and Optimal Blending methods are used to improve the achievable stability characteristics of the lateral-directional (MIMO) effective plant. The paper finishes with a brief discussion of how to design the prefilters for a MIMO system such as the one discussed here.

Background

This paper highlights some of the unusual problems encountered in recent research conducted at the Air Force Institute of Technology (AFIT) [6]. The research addresses the problem of controlling an X-29 type aircraft flying at high angles of attack (AOA). The X-29 is a forward-swept-wing advanced technology demonstrator which has shown exceptional maneuverability characteristics; due primarily to its *unstable* aerodynamic design. A highly sophisticated flight control system is *required* to control such an aircraft.

The flight control system discussed in this research uses *differential* canards to aid in lateral-directional control. This feature is not available on the X-29 aircraft. The models developed in the research are based on *limited* amounts of differential canard wind tunnel data taken on an X-29 scale model. Since the data is limited, the resulting dynamics models only *approximate* the open-loop dynamics of the actual X-29. As expected, these models are seen to possess RHP poles and zeros, thus making them both unstable and non-minimum phase.

The focus of this paper is to address the problems imposed by such RHP elements and present some specialized design methods to achieve at least marginally acceptable results. In this case, it turns out that designing for stability is a significant challenge, so design criteria such as handling qualities are not considered. Re-defining the problem with a different set of control variables is a viable option, but the point of this paper is to show what can be done with plants containing numerous RHP poles and zeros (often in close proximity to each other).

Aircraft Dynamics Models

The mathematical models used are based on a linearized state space representation of the aircraft's open-loop dynamics. Reference [1] discusses the derivation and application of linearized state space models. For this research, a single flight condition of Mach 0.3 and 20,000 ft altitude was chosen as the nominal operating point. Four models were developed about this flight condition by choosing four different AOA values: 20, 40, 50, & 60 degrees.

This paper illustrates the various design techniques by using selected cases, and only those models pertinent to the particular examples are discussed. The standard assumption is made to consider the longitudinal (pitching) mode and the lateral-directional (rolling & yawing) modes separately. The variables to be controlled are pitch rate (q), roll rate (p), and yaw rate (r). Reference [6] provides an in-depth discussion of how the state space models were developed and modified for this effort.

Frequency Dependent Weighting Matrix

A weighting matrix is required to *square-up* the effective plant, as shown in Figure 1. The three control inputs are distributed, with the appropriate relative weightings, among the seven aerodynamic control surfaces.

Figure 1: Block Diagram of Flight Control System

For most *conventional* aircraft, a matrix of constant elements is all that is required for the appropriate distribution. However, for aircraft such as this, different control surfaces are used in conjunction with each other to perform a specified flight maneuver. It

therefore becomes imperative that the control surfaces work together, or *in phase* with each other, to provide maximum control effectiveness. Thus, the weighting matrix must include *frequency dependent* elements were necessary, to ensure that the surfaces work in phase with each other.

For this particular application, the pitch control surfaces (symmetric canards, flaperons, & strakes) work in phase with each other, and thus require only constant weighting elements. The relative weightings are based on a knowledge of the relative effectiveness of the control surfaces to perform the desired flight maneuver.

The lateral-directional control modes require frequency dependent compensation, as the appropriate control surfaces (differential flaperons, rudder, & differential canards) do not initially work in phase with each other. This is evident by examining the open-loop step responses for yaw rate with 50 degree AOA (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Uncompensated Open-Loop Yaw Rate Step Responses ($\alpha = 50$)

The exponentially increasing sinusoids are clearly out of phase with each other. The goal of the compensation task is to get all three responses in phase *and* above and below the zero axis at the same time.

The typical approach to frequency compensation is to obtain a composite Bode plot and add the necessary pole/zero elements to bring the phase plots in close agreement with each other. Then, it is expected that the time domain step responses will be in phase. Unfortunately, the existence of RHP poles in the open-loop plant causes a problem with this approach.

Briefly, the unstable poles cause the transformation integral relating the time and frequency domains to be non-convergent. What this means is that even with the phases in close agreement there is no guarantee that the time domain responses will also be in phase.

The method used to overcome this problem is relatively straightforward. The roots of the open-loop plant are temporarily shifted to the left by an amount sufficient to place all poles in the stable left-half-plane (LHP). The compensation method discussed above is then applied to the shifted system. Figure 3 shows the frequency response of the shifted system prior to compensation. Poles and zeros are now added in an iterative fashion to align the phase plots as shown in Figure 4.

Figure 3: Uncompensated *Shifted* Yaw Rate Frequency Response ($\alpha = 50$)

Figure 4: Compensated *Shifted* Yaw Rate Frequency Response ($\alpha = 50$)

With the addition of simple first and second order lead/lag compensators, the roots are all shifted back by the original amount. The compensator elements (after shifting to the right) are included with the original open-loop plant and the step responses are obtained. As seen in Figure 5, the control surfaces are all working together as desired. The entire procedure is performed on a computer with the aid of a suitable computer aided design package.

Figure 5: Compensated Open-Loop Yaw Rate Step Responses ($\alpha = 50$)

Using this procedure, all of the frequency dependent compensation terms are developed, and along with the constant terms required for the pitch channel, the entire weighting matrix is formed. This matrix is combined with the original state space and control actuator models to form the overall effective plant (P_{eff}), as shown in Figure 1. Reference [6] presents the complete weighting matrix development.

Longitudinal Control System Design

An application of the QFT design technique is now shown for one of the longitudinal SISO plants. The extremely wide variations in plant parameters in this problem forces the need to design four different controllers, rather than a single controller to handle all four systems. Consequently, QFT templates are not used, as the plant in each case is precisely defined.

Figures 6 & 7 graphically show the relation between the loop transmission function $[L(s)]$, compensator $[G(s)]$, and effective plant $[P_{eff}(s)]$. With the effective plant defined, a desirable loop transmission function is developed and the required compensator transfer function is easily obtained by dividing out the effective plant.

Figure 6: Standard QFT Control System Notation

Figure 7: Alternate QFT Control System Notation

The example case chosen to demonstrate the procedure is the 40 degree AOA flight condition. The roots of the compensated effective plant are listed in Table 1.

roots(num40)	roots(den40)
0.0000 1	-0.0534±j0.1193
0.0458	0.3756
-0.3076	-0.8200
-20.0000	-20.0000
-20.0000	-20.0000
-32.4259	-20.0000
	-50.0000

Table 1: Roots of Longitudinal Effective Plant ($\alpha = 40$)

With the goal of minimizing the order of the compensator, $L(s)$ should contain at least some of the terms present in the effective plant. Table 1 shows that the effective plant for this case contains one RHP

pole and one RHP zero. It is decided that $L(s)$ should contain a zero at 0.0458 and a pole at 0.3756.

In addition, since $P_{eff}(s)$ has an excess of two poles over zeros, $L(s)$ should be designed with an excess of three. This is to ensure the desired high frequency characteristics $[L(\infty)=0]$. Therefore, $L(s)$ must contain a second order pair of poles and a single real pole. The second order pair may be real or complex, and the damping coefficient (ζ) and natural frequency (ω_n) may be arbitrarily chosen. An iterative routine is used on the computer to choose ζ and ω_n , and the value of the extra real pole. This is performed while analyzing the resulting Nichols and Bode plots of $L(s)$.

The Bode plot of $L(s)$ (Figure 8), is used to illustrate the design philosophy. The goal is to maximize the amount of loop transmission gain in the mid-frequency range, while maintaining reasonable gain and phase margins. It is known that in order to maximize the benefits of feedback, the loop transmission gain must be made as great as possible, at least in the frequency range of interest [4]. Maximizing the benefits of feedback reduces the sensitivity to disturbances [5]. There is a trade-off, however. The amount of allowable loop transmission gain is limited by the gain and phase margins. Increasing the gain reduces both stability margins, as discussed in Reference [2].

Figure 8: Bode Plot - Pitch Rate Loop Transmission ($\alpha = 40$)

By maximizing the loop transmission gain in the frequency range of interest (near $\omega=1$ rad/sec), and sacrificing gain (and the associated feedback benefits) in the low-frequency range, it is has been possible to achieve reasonable values of gain and phase margins for this case; +6.7 dB and +44.6 degrees, respectively.

The final loop transmission function (including gain adjustment) is given by:

$$L_{40q} = \frac{(0.5)(0.3756)(100)(s - 0.0458)}{(0.0458)(s - 0.3756)(s + 1)(s^2 + 10s + 100)}$$

The compensator transfer function is obtained by dividing $L(s)$ by the effective plant.

The next step is to close the loop by using the following expression:

$$T_L = \frac{L}{1 + L}$$

The Bode plot of the resulting expression is shown in Figure 9.

Figure 9: Bode Plot - Pitch Rate Closed Loop Transmission ($\alpha = 40$)

The final step is to design a prefilter to improve the time response characteristics. To achieve a desirable time response, the corresponding frequency response should be relatively flat (near zero-dB) up to a desired roll-off frequency. The gain should roll-off slowly above one rad/sec and then rapidly drop-off above 10 rad/sec.

The relatively simple prefilter given below is developed by adding poles and zeros as needed to bend the magnitude response of Figure 9 to approximate the desired frequency response characteristics.

$$F_{40} = \frac{1.180(s + 0.3)}{(s + 0.1)(s + 2)}$$

Note that the steady-state gain value of this prefilter is not unity, as is typically the case for prefilter designs. This is because the steady-state value of T_L

is less than one due to the previously discussed limitations imposed by the RHP zero [4]. As a result, the prefilter for this type of problem is used to compensate for the gain discrepancy in the low-frequency (steady-state) range. The Bode plot of the closed loop transmission function with prefilter is shown in Figure 10.

Figure 10: Bode Plot - Pitch Rate Closed Loop Transmission with Prefilter ($\alpha = 40$)

Lateral-Directional Control System

This section briefly discusses how the Singular-G and Optimal-Blending methods are used to improve the achievable stability characteristics of an unstable, non-minimum phase MIMO plant. Matrixx *System Build* [7] is used to generate the effective plants. This discussion looks at the 50 degree AOA lateral-directional plants. Since roll rate and yaw rate are both inputs and outputs, the MIMO plant consists of four different SISO plants.

Only the RHP roots of the four SISO plants are a concern at this point. The LHP roots are not a concern, since they do not affect the stability. Table 2 lists the RHP roots from all four SISO plants. In particular, only the RHP roots in close proximity to each other are a concern, since such proximity limits the range of gain over which the closed-loop system may be stabilized [4][3].

The Singular-G method is used to improve the allowable range of gain for a stable system. By use of the Singular-G compensator (Figure 11), the 2x2 MIMO plant is transformed into an *equivalent* (with

roots(num50)	roots(den50)
0.1173±j2.8344	0.4500±j3.1141
0.1443	0.7143±j3.8832
0.1686	0.7143±j3.8832
0.3469±j3.0648	
4.4312	
12.7288	
53.0418	

Table 2: RHP Roots of Lateral-Directional Effective Plants ($\alpha = 50$)

respect to stability) SISO plant. Then, by varying the parameters a, b, & c the equivalent plant may be modified so that the RHP poles and zeros are separated by a significant amount. In addition, it is possible to move some of the RHP roots into the LHP where they no longer pose a problem with stability.

Figure 11: Singular-G Compensator [5]

The resulting equivalent plant (Λ) is given by the equation below, where $P_{(x,y)}$ refers to each of the original 2x2 plants with x and y denoting the respective outputs and inputs [6].

$$\Lambda \equiv P_{(1,1)} a + P_{(1,2)} c + P_{(2,1)} ab + P_{(2,2)} bc$$

Table 3 lists the RHP roots of the modified equivalent SISO plant. One pair of poles has been moved into the LHP, as well as all but two of the RHP zeros. The remaining zeros are widely separated from the poles. Again, the LHP roots are not listed in the table.

With the effective plant now modified to improve its stability characteristics, the design proceeds with a step-by-step method for developing an *optimum* loop transmission function. The RHP poles and zeros in the plant may *not* be cancelled due to the uncer-

roots(num50)	roots(den50)
1.9130	0.4500±j3.1141
2.5237	0.7143±j3.8832

Table 3: RHP Roots of Equivalent Lateral-Directional Effective Plant ($\alpha = 50$)

tainties in the exact values. Therefore, the loop transmission function must contain the RHP poles and zeros of the effective plant (Table 3). The optimal-blending design procedure is based on *only* the RHP poles and zeros of the effective plant, since the stable LHP roots are not a concern for stability. The LHP roots may be cancelled with additional compensator terms, if desired.

A detailed derivation of the Optimal-Blending procedure is provided in Reference [3]. Only selected highlights of the procedure, as applied to this particular case, are presented here. The first step is to determine the minimum number of compensator poles (δ_{pc}) and zeros (δ_{zc}) from the number of effective plant RHP poles (δ_p) and zeros (δ_z), by use of the equations below.

$$\delta_{pc} = \delta_p + 2\delta_z - 2$$

$$\delta_{zc} = 2\delta_p + \delta_z - 2$$

In this case, with $\delta_p = 4$ and $\delta_z = 2$, the compensator must have six poles and eight zeros. The balanced portion of the loop transmission function must contain ten poles and ten zeros.

An optimal blending function [$\phi(s)$] is now defined as one side of the balanced portion of the loop transmission function. Thus, $\phi(s)$ is a function with five zeros and five poles. In this case, two zeros and four poles result from the effective plant. The values of the remaining roots must be determined. The optimal blending function is defined below.

$$\phi(s) = \left[\frac{(s - 1.9130)(s - 2.5237)}{(s - 0.7143 \pm j3.8832)(s - 0.4500 \pm j3.1141)} \right] * \left[\frac{(s^3 + As^2 + Bs + C)}{(s + D)} \right]$$

Proceeding with a design based on the above equation would result in a symmetric function about the $j\omega$ axis (i.e. marginal stability). To ensure stability, the $j\omega$ axis is offset into the left half plane by

replacing s with $v - 2$. Next, the numerator and denominator are expanded into even and odd monic polynomials, respectively, as shown below.

$$o_n + c_n e_n = v^5 + (8.4367A + B + 17.7012)v^3 + (17.7012B + 8.4367C)v + (8.4367 + A) * \\ \left(v^4 + \frac{(8.4367B + 17.7012A + C)v^2}{(8.4367 + A)} + \frac{(17.7012C)}{(8.4367 + A)} \right)$$

$$o_d + c_d e_d = v^5 + (64.7469 + 10.3286D)v^3 + (352.4153 + 195.2183D)v + (10.3286 + D) * \\ \left(v^4 + \frac{(195.2183 + 64.7469D)v^2}{(10.3286 + D)} + \frac{(352.4153D)}{(10.3286 + D)} \right)$$

Equating the like coefficients from their respective equations above yields four algebraic equations with four unknowns; the coefficients A, B, C, & D. With these values determined, the blending function is shifted back (by 2 units) to the original s -domain. The resulting blending function is shown below.

$$\phi(s) = \left[\frac{(s + 5.9130)(s + 6.5237)}{(s + 4.7143 \pm j3.8832)(s + 4.4500 \pm j3.1141)} \right] * \\ \left[\frac{(s + 2.9449)(s + 3.6660 \pm j4.3859)}{(s + 3.3750)} \right]$$

Finally, the *mirror image* of $\phi(s)$ about the chosen line of symmetry ($s = -2$) is given by:

$$\phi(s)_{im} = \left[\frac{(s - 1.9130)(s - 2.5237)}{(s - 0.7143 \pm j3.8832)(s - 0.4500 \pm j3.1141)} \right] * \\ \left[\frac{(s + 1.0051)(s + 0.3340 \pm j4.3859)}{(s + 0.6250)} \right]$$

These two equations are now combined into a single transfer function (the symmetric loop transmission function) and plotted on a root locus, as shown in Figure 12. The symmetry about $s = -2$ is readily apparent. It should be noted that the above equations result in this root locus pattern *only* for negative gain values.

The reason for plotting this function is to determine the range of loop transmission gain for which the closed-loop system is stable (i.e. no RHP closed-loop poles). As the gain magnitude is increased, the system becomes stable at $K = -0.82$ and again becomes unstable at $K = -0.98$. A reasonable choice for the loop transmission gain is the midpoint, $K = -0.90$.

Figure 12: Initial Optimal Blending Loop Transmission ($\alpha = 50$)

Close examination of Figure 12 reveals the locations of the *closed-loop* poles with this gain value, all ten of which are in the LHP; two on the real axis and eight on the $s = -2$ line of symmetry (two are just off the plot with the selected scaling).

Additional poles are required to make the loop transmission function a *proper* transfer function. Three poles are added to the loop transmission function to ensure that the compensated system has the desired high frequency characteristics. The three LHP poles are added far off ($s = -10000$) so that the symmetry near the origin is not disturbed greatly.

This technique results in achieving a stable loop transmission function with at least some degree of gain insensitivity. Although the insensitivity is rather low, this approach results in achieving the stability goal where conventional methods would fail when applied to a problem such as this [5]. The compensator (Ψ) is now obtained by dividing the loop transmission function by the effective plant. Recall that the effective plant still has many LHP roots that are not addressed in the above optimal-blending procedure. The compensator transfer function may be used to cancel out LHP roots.

Finally, the procedure for transforming the system back to a 2x2 MIMO system and designing the prefilter matrix is discussed briefly. Figure 13 shows the final arrangement of the system. Note that the prefilter affects only the commanded input signals and the compensator affects only the fed-back output states. The summation of these signals is the input to the effective plant.

Figure 13: Singular-G Compensator with Prefilter [5]

When the individual *original* $P_{i,j}$ transfer functions (each an element of a 2x2 matrix) are combined with the compensator transfer function, the 2x2 matrix of system transfer functions is obtained. Each element of this matrix can then be equated to a desired transfer function and the elements of the prefilter matrix can be obtained by algebraic methods. The desired transfer functions are typically developed by choosing dominant poles and zeros to obtain the desired time response characteristics. The procedure is discussed in Reference [2]. Also, the cross coupling effects, represented by the off-diagonal elements in the transfer function matrix, can be eliminated by proper selection of the prefilter terms. With the prefilter matrix defined, the MIMO design is complete.

Summary

This paper discusses how to use variations of QFT to achieve at least marginally acceptable results for unstable, non-minimum phase plants. The reader is referred to Reference [6] for a much more in-depth look at this particular group of problems. Further, References [3] & [4] provide a good theoretical discussion of the limitations of such systems and the use of these design methods to overcome those limitations.

References

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